

Lifelong Education for Teachers: A Tool for Achieving Effective Teaching and Learning in Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria

P. I. Adzongo, O. A. Aloga

Abstract—The purpose of the study was to examine lifelong education for teachers as a tool for achieving effective teaching and learning. Lifelong education enhances social inclusion, personal development, citizenship, employability, teaching and learning, community and the nation. It is imperative that the teacher needs to update his knowledge regularly to be able to perform optimally, since he has a major position in the inculcation of desirable elements in students, and the challenges of lifelong education were also discussed. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 80 teachers as sample from a population of 105 senior secondary school teachers in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. A 20-item self designed questionnaire subjected to expert validation and reliability was used to collect data. The reliability Alpha coefficient of 0.87 was established using Cronbach's Alpha technique, mean scores and standard deviation were used to answer the 2 research questions while chi-square was used to analyse data for the 2 null hypotheses, which states that lifelong education for teachers is not a significant tool for achieving effective teaching and lifelong education for teachers does not significantly impact on effective learning. The findings of the study revealed that, lifelong education for teachers can be used as a tool for achieving effective teaching and learning, and the study recommended among others that government, organizations and individuals should in collaboration put lifelong education programmes for teachers on the priority list. The paper concluded that the strategic position of lifelong education for teachers towards enhanced teaching, learning and the production of quality manpower in the society makes it imperative for all hands to be on "deck" to support the programme financially and otherwise.

Keywords—Lifelong Education, Tool, Effective Teaching and Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

EDUCATION has a vital role to play in the achievement of desired goals because it brings about change in an individual, the community and the society at large. The essence of education; however, is that it produces change in behaviour, transforms individual and society [1]. This transformation enables individuals in a society to be responsible and functional members of their society. The teacher has a major position towards achieving this

transformation; by inculcating desirable elements such as values, traditions accumulated knowledge skills and competencies, through the process of teaching. Therefore, it is imperative that the teacher needs to be knowledgeable and on a more regular basis requires knowledge update in order to be effective in performing his duties. This implies that lifelong education for teachers is a welcome development for Benue State and Nigeria as a whole, this is also because learning is an aspect of education which seeks continuity, therefore it starts and ends with life.

Lifelong education involves all forms, processes, strategies of education which includes; formal, non-formal and informal, it is therefore a continuous process which involves self motivation. It is therefore the most appropriate tool for achieving effective teaching and learning. This is in line with [2], [3] as they see "lifelong education as an organized education process whereby individuals and society develop their abilities, enrich their knowledge, improve their technical and professional qualifications or turn them in a new direction to bring about changes in full personal development and participates in social, economic and cultural development". On the other hand, the broad goals of secondary education as provided in [4] include to prepare individuals for useful living within the society and higher education. It is the first subsector of education with the objectives of preparing the recipients for participation in the world of work and economic activities. In Nigeria, presently the secondary system of education has three (3) arms: the junior secondary school, senior secondary school (SSS) and the technical college (TC). The curriculum of the senior secondary school is a progression for efficient and effective performance of the education acquired at the lower level, it is structured for academic progression and entrance into the world of work and again it consists of a comprehensive core curriculum designed to broaden the students' knowledge and outlook. The curriculum consists of 3 groups: A is made up of core subjects Arts, Sciences, Technical and Vocational Education, and Business Education, aimed at intellectual development of students in diversified manner Group B has eighteen elective subjects where a student has the option to select a minimum of one and maximum of two Vocational subjects. The essence is on completion of the senior secondary school, the student has at least one salable skill to engage in paid or self employment or progress further academically. Group C consists of non-vocational electives. Therefore, it is not out of place to state that this level of education is very important and requires

Adzongo P. I. is with Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria, She is now with the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education. (Phone: +2348061247365; e-mail: padzongo2015@gmail.com).

Aloga O. A. is with College of Education, Oju, Benue State, Nigeria. He is now with the Department of Educational Foundations (Phone: +2347030986341; e-mail: alogaustin@gmail.com).

knowledgeable teachers who are skilled and effective in performing their duties. Lifelong education for teachers of senior secondary schools will lead to a boost in their job performance and the achievement of the goals of secondary education in Benue State and Nigeria at large.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Teachers have the indispensable role to provide quality education but current developments in Nigeria today show low quality of students performance indicating the related role of the teacher, who is bedeviled by limited evidence of any general improvements of his status and, or the overall conditions of service. In addition, teacher training colleges are for long not in existence. However, professional developments of teachers' education are a vital recipe for achieving effective teaching and learning and for the realization of educational goals. In Nigeria, considerable number of teachers does not have any teacher education inform of training in the components of methodology, pedagogy, and practice. Although the Nigerian National policy on education [5], [6] stipulates in section 9 number 57, 58 and 59 that teacher education will continue to be given major emphasis in all educational planning because the educational system cannot rise above the quality of teachers. Teacher education programmes were to be structured to equip teachers for the effective performance of their duties.

Teachers especially at the primary and secondary school level is still a "mirage" in the face" of other competing social services and economic sectors as a result of misappropriation of funds, budget misplacement, priority placement by the political authorities in the country. Therefore, Nigeria is in dire need of a teachers' education programme to correct these anomaly. Hence, the advocacy for lifelong education for teachers; a tool for achieving effective teaching and learning in secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria, if the goals of secondary education are to be achieved wholly and in turn attain effective teaching and learning, towards the production of quality graduates and manpower for the society in the long run.

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to ascertain lifelong education for teachers as a tool for achieving effective teaching and learning, specifically the study sought to;

1. Determine the influence of lifelong education for teachers as a tool for effective teaching in senior secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area
2. Ascertain the impact of lifelong education for teachers on effective learning.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study;

1. How is lifelong education for teachers a tool for achieving of effective teaching?
2. What impact has lifelong education for teachers on effective learning?

V. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

H01.Lifelong education for teachers is not a significant tool for achieving effective teaching in senior secondary schools.

H02.Lifelong education for teachers does not significantly impact on effective learning.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. A simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 80 teachers from a population of 105 senior secondary school teachers in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The sample consisted 40 male and 40 female teachers.

A 20-item self designed questionnaire subjected to expert validation and reliability titled "Lifelong Education for Teachers for Achieving Effective Teaching and Learning Questionnaire" (LETAETLQ) was used to collect data. The questionnaire was divided into 2 sections, section A contained 10 structured statement items on effective teaching while section B had 10 structured statement items on effective learning with a 4-point modified rating scale of Strongly Agree –SA, Agree –A, Disagree –D and Strongly Disagree –SD with 4,3,2 and 1 points respectively. For instrument reliability questionnaires were administered to 20 head teachers of secondary schools in Gboko LGA of Benue State. And a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was determined using Crombach Alpha coefficient. The data collected were collated and analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation to answer the 2 research questions with a decision rate of 2.50 while chi-square was used to test the 2 null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance and 1 degree of freedom.

VII. RESULTS

The results of the findings are presented in Tables I and II.

Results of the findings in Table I showed that the respondents agreed to all the items with means scores above 2.50. This indicates that lifelong education for teachers is a tool to achieve effective teaching in senior secondary schools.

Results of the findings in Table II showed that 60 respondents agreed to the items as against 20 who disagreed with mean scores above 2.50. This indicates that lifelong education for teachers' impacts on effective learning.

TABLE I
MEAN SCORES AND STANDARD DEVIATION ON THE INFLUENCE OF LIFELONG EDUCATION FOR TEACHERS TO ACHIEVE EFFECTIVE TEACHING

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	DECISION
1	If I learn from more experienced teachers it will help my teaching.	2.84	0.36	Agree
2	By reading books on methods of teaching I will perform my duties better.	3.52	0.42	Agree
3	If I read news papers daily it will influence my teaching.	3.19	0.83	Agree
4	If I listen to news daily, it will improve my teaching.	2.67	0.48	Agree
5	If I attend workshops on a regular basis I will teach better.	2.56	0.66	Agree
6	If I attend conferences regularly I am bound to teach better.	3.01	0.63	Agree
7	If I am opportune to go on in-service training I will be a better teacher.	2.87	0.42	Agree
8	If I read about the use of instructional materials, I am bound to teach better.	2.93	0.75	Agree
9	I am an effective teacher because I like to know all about teaching.	3.21	0.84	Agree
10	I am an effective teacher because I learn from professional teachers.	3.22	0.44	Agree

TABLE II
MEAN SCORES AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS ON THE IMPACT OF LIFELONG EDUCATION FOR TEACHERS ON EFFECTIVE LEARNING

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	DECISION
11	If I teach using instructional material students will perform better.	3.25	0.94	Agree
12	If I am knowledgeable the students will learn better.	2.71	0.83	Agree
13	If I teach with skill the students learn better.	2.98	0.86	Agree
14	If I use the right methods to teach students learn faster and better.	2.67	0.93	Agree
15	If I teach with confidence students learn better.	3.02	0.74	Agree
16	If I teach better because I attend conferences students learn better.	3.65	0.48	Agree
17	I teach better when I read education books and students learn better.	3.75	0.94	Agree
18	If I teach better because I learnt from listening to the radio students learn better.	3.14	0.75	Agree
19	If I use the right methods to cover the syllabus students will learn better.	2.05	0.42	Agree
20	If am opportune to go for in-service training I will be a better teacher and students will learn better.	2.87	0.81	Agree

TABLE III
CHI-SQUARE TEST OF THE INFLUENCE OF LIFELONG EDUCATION FOR TEACHERS: A TOOL FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING

Opinions	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df	α -level	X^2	X^2 -tab	P	Decision
Impact	80	40	1	0.05	19	4.38	0.00	Significant
No Impact	0	40						
Total	80	80						

TABLE IV
CHI-SQUARE TEST OF THE IMPACT OF LIFELONG EDUCATION FOR TEACHERS ON EFFECTIVE LEARNING

Opinions	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df	α -level	X^2	X^2 -tab	P	Decision
Impact	80	40	1	0.05	5.5	5.05	0.00	Significant
No Impact	0	40						
Total	80	80						

Testing Hypothesis 1

Lifelong education for teachers is not a significant tool for achieving effective teaching.

Table III showed that the chi-square calculated value of 19, is greater than the chi-square tabulated value of 4.38, at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance and 1 degree of freedom.

The null hypothesis was rejected since the decision was significant. This implies that the alternative hypothesis is accepted indicating that Lifelong Education for Teachers is a significant tool for achieving effective teaching.

Testing Hypothesis 2

Lifelong Education for Teachers does not significantly impact on effective learning.

In Table II, the descriptive and inferential statistics of chi-square was computed and the result showed that 60 respondents agreed that lifelong education for teachers has significant impact on effective learning as against 20 respondents who disagreed.

Table IV showed that the chi-square calculated value of 5.5 is greater than the tabulated value of 5.05 at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance and 1 degree of freedom.

The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis which states that lifelong Education for Teachers significantly impacts on effective learning is accepted.

VIII. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the main findings of the research is based on the questions and hypotheses. The study revealed that

lifelong education for teachers is a positive tool for achieving effective teaching. This findings agree with [7] who in their study indicated that for effective teaching to be achieved, teachers should be properly trained, through interaction with professional colleagues, learn new ideas, new methods and be acquainted with new pedagogical discoveries.

The study also revealed that lifelong education for teachers' impacts positively on effective learning of secondary school students. This finding is in line with [8] constructive theory of learning which states that:

“Individual construct, meaning and understanding from their prior knowledge applied in particular context. Direct experience is a fundamental component of learning as reflection on that experience and gradual accumulation of knowledge structures overtime”.

Reference [9] supports by stating that students learn more when they are taught with effective teaching strategies which are exciting for students and requires them to do the conceptualizing, the organizing and the theorizing.

IX. CHALLENGES TO LIFELONG EDUCATION

Lifelong education is capital intensive because it is expensive, at whatever means or place for an individual to be educated. Therefore funding, misappropriation, political powers, priority budgeting, embezzlement and enthusiasm are some of the challenges of lifelong education. Teachers in Benue State also have peculiarities which reduce their zeal to be educated such as non-payment of salaries, motivation and other challenges include the ones listed by [10] to include the competition of other sectors of the economy; like defense, health, agriculture etc.

X. CONCLUSION

Lifelong education is the “key” for teachers to achieve effective teaching and learning, it transforms an individual a community and the society at large but even with the United Nations 26% Benchmark allocation Recommendation for education, the government of Nigeria still allocates far below it. However, it is imperative that teachers need lifelong education therefore the teachers, individuals, communities, organizations require encouragement to support government in funding education.

From the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Lifelong education for teachers should be a priority for teachers, individuals, NGOs, communities and the government.
2. The recommended budgetary allocation of 26% by UNESCO should be adhered to strictly by the government and even more.
3. All hands must be on deck to ensure the provision of lifelong education through provision of funds and other resources.
4. Teachers on their own need to motivate themselves with the zeal to embark on lifelong education.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nwokocho, L.K & Afianmagbaon, B.E. (2012). Financing lifelong education for community transformation in Nigeria. In A.O. Ayeni, U.G. Emetarom, A.O Okwori, J.A. Undie, & J.E Okon (Eds) managing education for National transformation Ibadan: His Lineage publishing house.
- [2] United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization and International labour organization (UNESCO & ILO) 2002. Technical and Vocational Education and Training for the 21st first century. UNESCO and ILO Recommendations. Paris. UNESCO & ILO.
- [3] Nwokocho, L.K & Afianmagbon, B.E 2009 Organization of education; the Nigeria Epoch. Okigwe; Whytem publishers
- [4] Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). National policy on education Abuja: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
- [5] National Policy on Education (2004) Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- [6] Adzongo, P.I. & Agbe, J.I. (2009) Analyzing educational policies in Nigeria, Makurdi: Selters Academic Press.
- [7] Akoja, I.E & Akoja, C.O (2014). Assessment of teacher's knowledge and utilization of information communication Technology (ICT) in the teaching of social studies in secondary schools in Makurdi metropolis Benue State. Journal of Educational foundations; 2,(2). Benue State University.
- [8] Rensrick, L. (2002). Education and learning to think, Washington DC: National Academy Press.
- [9] Brown, A.L & Palinscar, A. (2000). Guided cooperative learning and individual knowledge acquisition, Hillsdale, New Jersey: Erlbaum.
- [10] Edem, D.A (2006). Introduction to educational administration in Nigeria Ibadan: Spectrum Books.